

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPRESSIVE READING SKILLS IN FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: this article presents the theoretical basis of improving the methodological preparation of students for the development of expressive reading skills among future primary school teachers.

Key words: primary school students, teacher, reading skills, expressive reading, knowledge, skills, competence, methodical preparation, theoretical basis.

Introduction:

The native language and reading literacy classes taught in primary grades are the beginning and preparatory part of the subject of literature, which is taught in the subsequent stages. The content of the activities conducted in the reading classes is to teach the students to read correctly, clearly, meaningfully, express fluently with the speed of the specified criteria, the student's love for the motherland, the world around him, people's work and life. by enriching their knowledge such as instilling the ideas of heroism, bravery, and national independence into their consciousness, the knowledge, skills, and abilities of students are expanded, formed, and strengthened. Reading classes based on the requirements of the National Program, relying on life experiences and observations, and connecting them with life, ensures its effectiveness and conscious perception. It contains the educational and educational goals of reading and speech development, the content of native language and reading literacy classes by classes, methods of developing oral and written speech of reading skills, reading exercise issues such as communication of lessons with written speech are clearly included.

In the process of organizing reading classes, students' skills, which are the main form of the speech process, work on texts and books, the development of students' connected speech, and the development of speech culture are envisaged.

In the 1st grade, students learn to read the text consciously, correctly and syllabically. Special importance should be attached to remediation not only in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, but also in all subjects and extracurricular activities. Children learn to correctly answer questions about the works they read. We know that work on the text is carried out under the guidance of the teacher.

In the 2nd grade, students learn the ability to read whole words by heart. Correct and expressive reading is achieved. The pace of reading is getting faster. In this class, students read some parts of the text and short stories independently. Working on the text becomes more complicated. Under the guidance of the teacher, children determine the main content of the work, learn to find words and phrases that express the behavior of the characters, and describe events with words. Their demand for vocabulary increases.

In the 3rd grade, the ability to read words completely is formed. It is required to correctly choose words, to correctly use the connection of words in the construction of sentences.

In the 4th grade, students should be able to read words without syllables, read the text quickly, correctly and consciously. Students should not be allowed to study in groups in this class. Children should independently retell the content of the read text, be able to make a simple plan based on the text, distinguish its main content, and retell the read text in full.

Children's literary pronunciation norms are formed in the process of expressive reading and mutual speech activity. Activation of students' speech, correct use of grammatical forms of speech and correct pronunciation help children's speech to be fluent. Factors affecting the teaching of expressive reading include:

- a) *ability to use breath correctly;*
- b) *good knowledge of literary language pronunciation norms;*
- d) *includes correct and accurate pronunciation of syllables and sounds.*

Expressive reading plays a key role for the teacher as one of the important methods of thorough mastering of various artistic and practical texts. Expressive reading does not allow students to get bored in classes, on the contrary, it activates them, increases their interest in artistic works, and awakens their passion for literature.

There are basically two ways to teach students to read expressively in reading classes:

1. In the course of the lesson, based on the character of different texts, teach students to read expressively;
2. Organization of special expressive reading programs due to the reduction of hours given to study materials.

In short, expressive reading includes such tasks as educating elementary school students' interest in art, teaching reading skills, developing and forming a culture of behavior that is considered an integral part of social life during the formation of aesthetic taste. Expressive reading means not only reading each word, phrase and sentence in a literary work with a beautiful pronunciation, correctly and fluently, but also reading with understanding, depending on the general situation of the given text. In addition to the genre characteristics of the work of art, it is also required taking into account its specific internal structure and content. To achieve this, it is necessary to teach elementary school students to work deeply with the text.

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